

alcoholic medium. After refluxion for two hours, 3-aldehydosalicyledene cyanoacetyl hydrazone (3-ASCAH) separated as a crystalline compound. The deep yellow coloured needles of this Schiff base were purified by repeated crystallisation from alcohol. The compound is soluble in alcohol and dioxane with sharp m.p. 208°.

Apparatus : The absorbance measurements were done on Beckman DU spectrophotometer Model 109200 using a matched pair of 1 cm cuvettes. The Metrohm pH meter Model E-350A with wide range glass calomal electrode was used. Buffer solutions prepared of potassium hydrogen phthalate and borax were used for standardisation of the pH meter.

Stock Solutions :

Stock solution of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ of 3-aldehydosalicyledene cyanoacetyl hydrazone prepared by dissolving the requisite amount in ethanol. Standard solution of Fe(III) of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ was prepared in double distilled water and estimated by EDTA³.

Sequence of Addition of Reagents : No change in the absorbance or colour intensity of the complex was observed if the order of addition of reactants was changed.

Absorbance Spectrum : A solution of 1 ml of Iron stock solution and 1 ml of 3-ASCAH was adjusted to pH 5 while diluting with water to exactly 10 ml maintaining the 50% aqueous-ethanol (v/v) medium. An appropriate blank was prepared in a similar manner except that water was added in place of Iron solution. Absorbance measurements were made in the region 350-600 nm after the adjustment of pH. The reagent showed a sharp absorbance band due to Iron³⁺-3-ASCAH complex at 370 nm with the molar absorptivity of 1.292×10^5 litres/mole cm.

Effect of pH : The absorption characteristics of the complex in the pH range 4-5 showed a maximum colour with 3-ASCAH. The pH was adjusted with buffer.

Conformity to Beer's Law :

A number of solutions containing varying amount of Iron and 0.2 ml of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ 3-ASCAH solution at pH 5 ± 0.1 were prepared and tested for the confirmation of the colour system for Beer's Law, which was seen to be followed at 370 nm over the concentration range 6 to 70 ppm of Iron for 1.0 cm cells; the absorbance readings were low below 6 ppm of Iron.

Sensitivity and Molar Absorptivity of the Complex : The spectrophotometric sensitivity of the colour

reaction in terms of Sandell's definition⁴ is $0.043 \mu\text{g}$ of Iron per cm^2 for $\log I_0/I = 0.001$. The molar absorptivity calculated from a plot of Beer's Law is 1.292×10^5 litres/mol. cm. at 370 nm.

Effect of Diverse ions and Media : The effect of different inorganic and organic species was studied for solutions containing 10 ppm of Iron and 0.2 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the reagent and the varying concentrations of each ion were tested in a total volume of 10 ml at pH 5. The absorbance measurements showed that Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} interfere in this colour reaction even in small quantities. The presence of acetate ion in more than 0.01 M increases the error by 1.5%.

The alcohol contents must not be less than 35% (v/v), otherwise the reagent is precipitated.

Conclusion : 3-ASCAH may prove to be a versetile reagent for the determination and estimation of Iron spectrophotometrically in presence of several anions and cations.

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A Novel Spray Reagent for Plant Pigments

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THE present investigation was carried out with a view to find some new spray reagents for detecting the presence of hydroxyl groups adjacent to carbonyl groups in the quinones and flavones. This was achieved by paper chromatographic procedures involving the use of *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water $\left(4 : 1 : 5 \frac{\text{v}}{\text{v}}\right)$ as solvent and 1% aqueous sodium vanadate as spray reagent when the plant pigments were present in amounts of at least $5 \mu\text{g}$ each.

This reagent has shown better results on comparing with the following popular spray reagents¹⁻⁴ viz. ammonia vapours, *p*-toluene sulphonic acid, iodine vapours, methanolic aluminium chloride, methanolic sulphuric acid, 1%

NOTES

TABLE 1

Substance	R _f	Colour observed	Fluorescence in U.V light
Taxifoline	0.78	LB	BL
Taxifoline-galactoside	0.73	LB	BL
Kaempferol	0.83	Y	DB
Quercetin	0.78	Y	DB
Rhamnetin	0.80	Y	BL
5,7-dihydroxy 4'-methoxy flavone	0.50	Y	BL
7-hydroxy flavone	0.00	—	BL
5,7-dihydroxy flavone	0.67	LY	LB
5,7,4'-trihydroxy 3,6,3'-trimethoxy flavonol	0.61	LY	LB
Avicularin	0.70	Y	LB
Quercitrin	0.82	Y	LB
Rutin	0.56	Y	LY
Penta methyl quercetin	0.71	—	BL
5-hydroxy 7,3',4'-trimethoxy flavonol	0.38	Y	DB
2-hydroxy 1 : 4 naphthaquinone	0.84	LB	BL
Chrysophanol	0.76	P	LB
Emodine	0.64	LP	LP
Physcion monomethyl ether	0.11	P	LP

methanolic sodium hydroxide, 5% aqueous sodium carbonate solution. Only ammonia vapours and 1% methanolic sodium hydroxide were found almost equal in performance in comparison to that of sodium vanadate. The new reagent is specific for the detection of hydroxyl group adjacent to carbonyl groups in quinones, flavones and their *o*-glycosides even at concentration of 5 μ g. The

pigments having no hydroxyl groups adjacent to the carbonyl groups and completely methylated flavonoids do not give colour reaction with the reagent.

The R_f values, colour with the spray reagent and colour in the UV light are given in Table 1.

LB=Light Brown, BL=Bluish, Y=Yellow, DB=Dark Brown, LY=Light Yellow, P=Pink, LP=Light Pink.

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